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Supporting Information

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Fabrication of Biophotovoltaic Devices

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Rational design of a photosystem I photoanode for the fabrication of biophotovoltaic devices

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Figure S1. Photochronoamperometric measurements of a PSI LB film on a P-vio-modified Au electrode (Au/P-vio/PSI-LB) in the presence of DCPIP and ascorbate (a). The same configuration but with an additional top layer of P-Os (Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os) was investigated in the presence of ascorbate (b). A magnification for the responses obtained at applied potentials of 200 mV and 150 mV vs. SHE is presented in panels (c) and (e) for the Au/P-vio/PSI-LB electrode and in panels (d) and (f) for the Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os electrode. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 50 μM DCPIP and 40 mM ascorbic acid (for a, c, and e) or only 40 mM ascorbic acid (for b, d, and f). Illumination with white light during the times indicated by the yellow-shaded regions.

Figure S2. Oxidation of ascorbate at the electrode surface. Bare Au-coated Si wafer in the presence of 40 mM ascorbic acid. Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0. Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹. Inset: magnification of the response for the forward scan.

Figure S3. Comparison of photocurrent responses for a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode using different glucose concentrations in the electrolyte solution. a) 10 mM glucose, average response for three different electrodes: $(5.0 \pm 0.8) \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. b) 5 mM glucose. c) 2 mM glucose, average response for two different electrodes: $(5.6 \pm 0.9) \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. The green-shaded regions represent the standard deviation between measurements. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0. $E_{app} = 200$ mV vs. SHE. Illumination with white light during the times indicated by the yellow-shaded regions.

Figure S4. Representative photochronoamperometric measurements for a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode prepared using the opposite orientation for the PSI-LB monolayer (a) and for an electrode in the absence of the P-vio film (Au/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx) (b). Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 10 mM glucose. Illumination with white light during the times indicated by the yellow-shaded regions.

Figure S5. a) Photocurrent response for a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode under different illumination wavelengths, ranging from 313 nm to 750 nm. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 3 mM glucose. $E_{app} = 200$ mV vs. SHE. The sample was illuminated with each wavelength for 10 s, as indicated by the colored regions in the graph. b) Power of light reaching the sample as a function of illumination wavelength.

Figure S6. Photochronoamperometric measurements for a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode under ambient air conditions. Electrolyte: air-equilibrated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0. a) In the presence of 10 mM glucose. b) In the absence of glucose. Illumination with white light during the times indicated by the yellow-shaded regions.

Figure S7. Long-term stability for Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrodes under Ar atmosphere and in the presence of ambient air. The initial and final periods of the measurement under intermittent irradiation for a period of 90 min are presented in panels (a) and (b), respectively. $E_{app} = 200$ mV vs. SHE. Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 10 mM glucose. Illumination with white light during the times indicated by the yellow-shaded regions. Note that the currents have been normalized for a straightforward comparison of stability over time.

Figure S8. Cyclic voltammograms for a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode in dark and light conditions. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 10 mM glucose. Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S9. Representative photochronoamperometric measurement for a PSI-LB film over a P-vio-modified Au electrode, with an additional layer of the cross-linking agent PEGDGE, and with a top layer of GOx embedded in P-Os (Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/PEGDGE/P-Os/GOx). Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 10 mM glucose. Illumination with white light during the times indicated by the yellow-shaded regions.

Figure S10. a) Cyclic voltammograms for a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode in the absence and presence of glucose in the electrolyte solution. b) Cyclic voltammograms in the absence and presence of glucose obtained for a similar electrode as before but fabricated using a layered deposition of P-vio (for details see main text). Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0. Dark conditions. Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S11. a) Characterization of the GOx/HRP-based biocathode. The bioelectrode was operated under a passive air-breathing configuration while the electrolyte solution was either open to ambient air or bubbled with Ar. Scan rate: 5 mV s^{-1} . b) Amperometric response for a biocathode upon addition of glucose into the cell. $E_{app} = 300 \text{ mV vs. SHE}$. Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0.

Figure S12. a) Polarization and b) power curves obtained for a biophotovoltaic cell assembled by combination of a Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/P-Os/GOx electrode as biophotoanode with a GOx/HRP air-breathing biocathode. Electrolyte: Ar-purged 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 10 mM glucose. Illumination with white light.

Figure S13. a) Power curves obtained under dark conditions for cells assembled by integration of three different Au/P-vio/PSI-LB/PEGDGE/P-Os/GOx electrodes as biophotoanode in combination with freshly prepared GOx/HRP air-breathing biocathodes. Data labelled as (A) correspond to the biophotoanode shown in Figure 4c (main text). Data labelled as (B) and (C) correspond to the biophotoanodes presented in panels b and c, respectively. b,c) Electrochemical characterization of biophotoanodes by means of cyclic voltammetry under dark and light conditions. Electrolyte: Ar-purged 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, containing 3 mM glucose.